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centre for functional and
surface functionalized glass

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Book of Abstracts

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Oxidation behavior and thermal shock resistance of PDC coatings

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ABSTRACT

This work is aimed at the investigation of the oxidation behavior and thermal shock resistance of ferritic stainless steel grade AISI 441 and polymer-derived ceramic (PDC) protective coatings. Double-layer coatings of a PDC bond coat below a PDC top coat with glass and ceramic passive fillers were studied at temperatures up to 1000 °C in a flow-through atmosphere of synthetic air and in air saturated with water vapor. Experimental methods have been developed and used to investigate the thermal shock behavior of the PDC coatings. To determine it, the quenching technique is a typical method. After heating in a furnace at 900 °C for 1 h, the samples were quenched in air and water. The Fe, Cr₂O₃, TiO₂, and spinel (Mn,Cr)₃O₄ phases were identified by XRD on oxidized steel substrates in both atmospheres. In the cases of the coated samples, m- ZrO₂, c- ZrO₂, YAG, and crystalline phases (Ba(AlSiO₄)₂-hexacelsian, celsian) were identified. Scratch tests performed on both coating compositions revealed strong adhesion after pyrolysis as well as after oxidation tests in both atmospheres. After testing in the water vapor atmosphere, Cr ions diffused through the bond coat, but no delamination of the coatings was observed. After thermal shock resistance tests in air and water, no damage or cracks were visible on the surface or at the metal/base layer interface. The very good behavior of these layers under thermal loading was due to the similar coefficients of thermal expansion of the layers and steel.

Keywords: coatings, oxidation, PDCs, stainless steel, thermal shock

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Characterization of La₂Ce₂O₇ powder synthesized by modified Pechini sol-gel method

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ABSTRACT

Thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) are usually utilized as protective coatings in the hot parts of gas turbines to protect the underlying superalloy from harsh environment [1]. In recent years, a lot of investigations have been dedicated to the search for alternative ceramic material for TBCs to replace the conventional yttria stabilized zirconia (YSZ). Lanthanum cerium oxide (La₂Ce₂O₇) has attracted increasing interest as a promising material for TBCs because of its high phase stability and potential capability to be operated above 1250 °C [2]. Moreover, La₂Ce₂O₇ exhibits lower thermal conductivity and higher thermal expansion coefficient than YSZ [3]. In this work, La₂Ce₂O₇ powder was prepared by modified Pechini sol-gel method using commercial lanthanum oxide and cerium nitrate. The synthesized La₂Ce₂O₇ powder was heat treated at the temperatures of 1000-1400 °C for 6 hours and investigated as a material for TBC applications: powder morphology, chemical composition and crystal structure were studied.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the prepared powder revealed agglomerated structure consisting of uniformly distributed grains with size up to 10 µm. The irregular and angular shape of the grains resulted from the crushing process. Energy dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (EDXS) analysis indicated chemical composition of the prepared LC powder to be similar to the stoichiometric ratio of the La₂Ce₂O₇. The fluorite structure of the La₂Ce₂O₇ powder was confirmed by X-Ray diffraction analysis (XRD) showing intensive peaks corresponding to the pure La₂Ce₂O₇ phase. There was always a single crystal structure in the synthesized powder after heat treatment over the entire temperature range. No additional peaks belonging to La₂O₃ were observed, confirming the formation of solid solution of La₂O₃ in CeO₂.

Keywords: La₂Ce₂O₇, Pechini method, TBCs

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Sol-gel based thin film coatings for metallic and glass-ceramic surfaces for optoelectronic applications

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ABSTRACT

Sol-gel coatings have been used for variety of applications such as corrosion inhibition, energy storage and are even employed as an important procedure in optoelectronic devices, such as photovoltaics, e-ink, and sensor devices. Certain e-ink devices are based on similar physical phenomena compared to batteries with examples of Li-WO₃ intercalation devices, which strongly resemble Li-ion batteries in its operation. Majority of optoelectronic devices use at least one optically transparent electrode (OTE), counter electrode and electrolyte, which interacts with the active component applied on the OTE. Recently, novel type of electrochemical geometry structure enables to manufacture devices without the use of OTE and is based solely on thin-sheet metal foil, which can be used to build durable devices. Here, authors present a possible transfer of existing sol-gel preparation procedures that are being used on functionalized glass, such as fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) onto the sheet metal-based devices that use either stainless steel or other metal foils. Prepared coatings should have dual purpose, with primary purpose enabling coated material to be used for different electrochemical or electroactive applications, such as batteries or electronic ink, as well as passive applications (corrosion resistance, improved durability...), depending on prepared sol-gel film.

Keywords: sol-gel, optoelectronic devices, glass coatings, metal coatings.

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Multifunctional Plasma Coatings

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ABSTRACT

Plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) technique has been known as a process to deposit a wide variety of coatings. Recently, one of the important coatings manufactured by PECVD in a gas mixture of hydrocarbon and argon is plasma polymer coating. By adjusting the process parameters, a wide range of the mechanical, physical, chemical and even biocompatibility properties can be achieved. Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coating is one of the main membranes of the plasma coatings exhibiting high hardness and low coefficient of friction which are used in automobile engine components and petrochemical industries to provide efficient energy consumption by decreasing the wear and corrosion. In this report, it will be shown our recent results which have been done by different types of PECVD techniques to produce a wide range of plasma coatings for different purposes. It will explain how to promote the wear resistant of the DLC coatings by doping nitrogen in the structure. Additionally, the biocompatibility, hardness, and surface energy of the plasma polymer coatings can be modified by controlling the PECVD process parameters. It will evaluate that the role of the nitrogen incorporation and applied voltage for improving the wear resistant, mechanical properties and biocompatibility of the coatings.

Keywords: plasma, coating, tribology, biocompatibility, nitrogen.

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Preparation of YAG and yttria- alumina suspensions

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ABSTRACT

This work presents experimental data and its interpretation regarding the preparation of YAG and yttria-alumina suspensions, intended to prepare transparent YAG ceramic by the slip casting method. YAG powders used for this work, were prepared by two different techniques – combustion synthesis where the particles have the size approximately 40 nm and radiation-induced preparation of YAG doped by cerium (particle size around 160 nm). Moreover, suspension consisting of yttria and alumina, for reaction sintering of YAG) was optimized.

Suspensions were de-agglomerated in planetary ball mill and ball mill, respectively. Two types of dispersant were used: Darvan C-N and Dolapix CE64, respectively. In the results, particle size distribution, and viscosimetry of prepared suspensions are discussed.

Keywords: suspensions, YAG

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Densification of nanocrystalline Y_2O_3 shaped by different methods

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ABSTRACT

Translucent yttria ceramics were fabricated from a commercial nano- Y_2O_3 powder. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analyses confirmed that the as-received powder comprised large agglomerates composed of primary particles characterized by a crystallite size between 25-35 nm. The as-received powder was dispersed in ethanol using ball milling and the addition of Polyethylene glycol (PEG). The effects of Y_2O_3 solid loading and the dispersant concentration of powder were studied in terms of the viscosity of suspensions and the size of primary aggregates. The suspension was afterward used to produce cylindrical samples by slip casting (SC) and pressure filtration (PF). Green pellets were also produced from dried and granulated suspensions using uniaxial pressing (UP) for comparison. The samples were sintered using a two-stage regime consisting of initial heat-treatment at 1700°C for 30 min followed by an isothermal sintering at 1400°C. Final Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) of sintered samples at 1550 °C for 2 h under 200 MPa eliminated porosity and produced highly dense Y_2O_3 ceramic (~99 %).

Keywords: Densification; Grain size; Shaping methods; Sintering; Y_2O_3

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Y₂O₃ based fluorescent ceramics materials: a comparison

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ABSTRACT

The Y₂O₃ ceramic materials doped by 0, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5, and 4.0 at.% of Zn²⁺ were prepared and influence of the amount of additive on fluorescence properties was investigated. Materials doped by Zn²⁺ featured high intensity broad emission band in visible part of electromagnetic spectra centred at 534nm (warm white light) when irradiated by UV radiation of 374nm wavelength. The strongest intensity of luminescence was observed for materials doped between 3 to 4 at.% of Zn²⁺. The possible fluorescence mechanism is based on excitation of electrons from valence band to conductive band of ZnO and subsequent relaxation through intermediate states of oxygen vacancies V_O⁰, V_O⁺¹ and V_O⁺².

Additionally the microstructure was examined by SEM coupled with EDXS and EBSD methods. EDXS revealed Zn concentrated into domains; the Zn is below detection limit outside of these domains. EBSD identified these domains as a discrete ZnO (zincite) grains in the matrix of Y₂O₃. EDXS also revealed places with heightened concentrations of zinc on places where EBSD revealed only Y₂O₃. This is usually caused by low information depth of EBSD method; EDXS identifies probably zincite grains from greater depths than EBSD can.

Keywords: Y₂O₃, ZnO, EBSD, Luminescence

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The applied approach to glass foams from inorganic non-metallic waste

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ABSTRACT

The inorganic non-metallic waste from industry, i.e. culets, ashes, dusts, slurries, until recently eluded the interest of manufacturers for any environmentally savvy solutions besides landfilling. Yet, on the other side, this waste is of interest for numerous scientific studies, listing its possible utilization to more or less functionalized and attractive-for-manufacture material groups. Example of such are glass and glass-ceramic foams based on this inorganic waste. Glass foams are currently manufactured industrially, yet their technological cost has oftentimes disputable environmental impact. The presentation focuses on glass-ceramic foam works done at FunGlass and University of Padova, in the aspect of used materials, their characterization and possibility of their processing into glass-ceramic foams. Mineralogy, mechanical properties, presence of heavy metals and overall possible manufacturing amounts will be discussed in the consideration against the actual possible applicability for technological scaling off from the laboratory table.

Keywords: alkali-activation, glass foams, waste glass

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Surface degradation of historical glass caused by interaction with the surrounding environment

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ABSTRACT

Solving the problems of corrosion and deterioration of historical glasses is a long-standing concern for researchers, conservators, and curators [1]. In archaeological glass objects, environmental factors such as soluble salts, carbonates, humidity, and oxygen/salt ratio can be responsible for the corrosion process [2]. According to the literature with historical, archaeological and glass conservation background, glass corrosion is often named as a “glass disease” or “glass illness” [3,4]. The set of historical glass samples was studied especially in terms of surface degradation caused by interaction with the surrounding environment or due to another conditions. The surfaces of historical glass samples were studied by micro-Raman spectroscopy, optical microscopy (OM), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) including Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). The obtained results show the significant influence of the environmental parameters and glass composition on the vulnerability to corrosion.

Keywords: Glass corrosion, Historical glass, Raman spectroscopy, Optical microscopy, AFM

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Prediction of ion release from glass using thermodynamic modeling

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ABSTRACT

The SBF (simulated body fluid), commonly used medium for bioactivity prediction (1), is in a metastable state and ready for precipitation of hydroxyapatite (HAP). The PHREEQC software developed for geochemical calculation (2) was selected as a tool for calculating the composition of SBF and confirming the concentrations of dissolved species, when oversaturation towards HAP is achieved. In the first step, the TRIS buffer as a new phase was defined and included in the PHREEQC to simulate preparation of SBF solution at the pH (7.4). The comparison of the concentration of selected elements in human plasma, SBF and calculated using PHREEQC is in Table 1.

Tab. 1: Ion concentrations of human plasma, SBF and calculated using PHREEQC.

	Na^+	K^+	Mg^{2+}	Ca^{2+}
<i>Human plasma</i>	142	5.0	1.5	2.5
<i>SBF</i>	142	5.0	1.5	2.5
<i>PHREEQC</i>	142	4.98	1.5	2.5

The PHREEQC software was used to simulate the static test and dissolution of the zinc doped 45S5 bioactive glass. The method of its preparation and characterization of the sample is fully described in the dissertation thesis of Švančárková (3). The zinc concentration determined in the leachates from the static test was very low and close to limit of quantification for ICP OES (optical emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma) method. Low durability of bioactive glasses would lead to the assumption that the zinc is released congruently along with other ions when the glass was dissolves. Based on the amount of released network former element (Si), the input amount of dissolved glass for PHREEQC simulations was estimated as 10% of the total initial amount and dissolution was performed sequentially in ten steps to simulate dissolution of the sample during the test.

Experimental weight was 75 mg used in the static test and dissolved in 50 mL of SBF. Using PHREEQC, the composition of the resulting solution was calculated and based on the calculation of saturation indices it was predicted which phases could be supersaturated due to the newly formed composition of the solution. The saturation indexes are expressed as a logarithm of the ratio of ion activity product to solubility constant. If the SI value is greater than 0, the solution is supersaturated with respect to the mineral, $SI < 0$ means undersaturated and when $SI = 0$, the solution is saturated, i.e. in equilibrium.

The result of the simulation is exported in the output file that defines the chemical characteristics of solution in detail as pH, the mass of solution, temperature, ionic strength, etc. An important part of the output file is a list of the total concentration of dissolved species including the molar concentration and a list of possible phases and their composition.

It has been found that several minerals can be supersaturated, namely: hydroxyapatite $Ca_5(OH)(PO_4)_3$, $ZnSiO_4$, antigorite $Mg_{48}Si_{34}O_{85}(OH)_{62}$, hopeite $Zn_3(PO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, zinc ZnO , etc.

The next simulation was set up to achieve equilibrium for all these phases, i.e. the same amount dissolved and the same amount precipitated. The exported zinc concentration and the precipitated amounts of hydroxyapatite and $ZnSiO_4$ are in Table 2. It was found that the precipitation of HA took place from the beginning and the precipitation of $ZnSiO_4$ started later when with increasing zinc concentration, the saturation index of zinc silicate has reached positive values. With proceeding dissolution decrease of zinc concentration is found in the overview of simulation result.

Table 2: The overview of the results of the individual dissolution steps.

Step of dissolution	conc. Zn (mol/L)	amount of precipitated HA (mol)	amount of precipitated Zn ₂ SiO ₄ (mol)
1	2.75E-06	1.15E-05	0.00E+00
2	5.51E-06	1.21E-05	0.00E+00
3	8.26E-06	1.27E-05	0.00E+00
4	1.10E-05	1.32E-05	0.00E+00
5	1.38E-05	1.38E-05	0.00E+00
6	1.65E-05	1.44E-05	0.00E+00
7	1.93E-05	1.49E-05	0.00E+00
8	1.72E-05	1.54E-05	1.20E-07
9	1.26E-05	1.58E-05	3.04E-07
10	8.95E-06	1.62E-05	4.65E-07

These calculations open up the discussion that not only hydroxyapatite can be formed from the SBF solution used for prediction of bioactivity but proving the formation of other minerals can bring information about the overall amount of released ion, especially when a therapeutic effect is expecting for further bio-response studies.

Keywords: bioactive glass, leaching tests, PHREEQC, simulated body fluid

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The influence of various acid etching treatments on the 3Y-TZP ceramics surface roughness

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ABSTRACT

The superior flexural strength and fracture toughness of zirconia-based ceramics, combined with the possibility to be accurately processed to complex geometries using CAD–CAM technologies or low-pressure injection moulding is a very promising material in dental implantology and could be an alternative for titanium dental implants [1, 2]. However, the future of dental implants greatly depends on the successful initial osseointegration shortly after implantation. The surface properties and topographical features are considered as a critical parameter for enhancing the osseointegration [3]. Surface treatment methods currently applied to zirconia-based ceramic implants mainly copy procedures applied to titanium implants, where etching is performed in very acidic solutions (nitric/hydrofluoric/hydrochloric) [4]. Hydrofluoric acid is a very hazardous and harmful acid for human health, so it is important to find a better and safer protocol to improve surface properties in zirconia-based dental ceramic materials. In this work, the effect of various acids on the surface topography was assessed. The preliminary study was carried out to determine which combinations of concentration were more suitable to achieve rapidly an appropriate roughness on the surface of the studied sample. Commercial 3Y-TZP powder (TZ-3Y-E Tosoh Co., Japan) was uniaxially pressed (50 MPa), sintered in air at 1500 °C-1h and polished down to 1 µm. The surface acid etching tests were carried out in Teflon vessels using 5 ml of different acids (Table 1.).

Table 1. Acids used in the surface etching procedure.

	Acid/ acids combination used	stoichiometric ratio
1	HF(40%)	-
2	HNO ₃ (52.5%): HF (40%)	5:1
3		5:2
4	HNO ₃ (65%): HCl (36%): HF (40%)	5:2:1
5	HNO ₃ (65%): HCl (36%)	3:1
6	HBF ₄ (48%)	-
7	HNO ₃ (52.5%): HBF ₄ (48%)	5:1
8		5:2
9	HNO ₃ (52.5%): HCl (36%): HBF ₄ (48%)	5:2:1
10	HNO ₃ (65%): HBF ₄ (48%)	49:1

Samples were completely covered by the solution and etched up to 6 hours in two different experimental conditions: in the room temperature (21°C) and in the ultrasonic bath (40°C) respectively. Only one sample was used for each condition and acid treatment. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM Bruker Innova®) in tapping mode was used in order to characterize the topography of 3Y-TZP samples before and after etching. AFM measurements were performed on 20 µm × 20 µm areas (resolution: 1024 × 1024 pixels). The starting surface average roughness (Ra) and the root mean square of the surface (RMS) roughness (Rq) after polishing for prepared samples is as follows: Ra = 15 ± 1 nm, Rq = 12 ± 1 nm. The increase of the surface roughness is observed after each acid etching procedure. The highest surface roughness (Ra = 513 ± 190 nm) is observed in the sample, immersed in the combination of nitric, hydrochloric, and hydrofluoric acid for 6 hours in the ultrasonic bath (40 °C). Using high concentrated hydrofluoric acid (HF) acid leads to the fastest etching. Hydrofluoroboric acid (HBF₄) is a promising substitute for HF acid, however, its reactivity is better with using an ultrasonic bath and increase temperature.

Keywords: Zirconia-based ceramics, acid etching, AFM

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Structural analysis of radiopaque bioactive glass 45S5[®] for biomedical applications

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ABSTRACT

Bioactive glasses (BG) have become one of the most researched materials in biomedical applications due to the combination of their outstanding bioactivity, biocompatibility, and mechanical properties [1]. From various glass fabrication methods, melt quenching is a versatile and effective route to control the chemical composition of the BG [2]. As an implantable material, the integration of BG on hard tissue in *in-vivo* models may be evaluated through x-ray radiographs [3], [4]. The image contrast on this evaluation plays an important role and it can be enhanced by the inclusion of a heavy and biocompatible element on the glass through melt and fast quenching. Previous contributions have researched the influence of Bi₂O₃ on the radiopacity of 45S5[®] or similar BG [5]–[7] but the information on the effect of progressive additions of Bi₂O₃ up to 15 wt. % on the melt-quenching 45S5[®] glass and the amount that represents the appropriate radiopacity without causing detrimental changes on the glass features is still missing.

The present work shows the effect of Bi₂O₃ on the bioactivity, structure, thermal properties, and radiopacity of BG with a similar composition of 45S5 obtained by melt quenching. Progressive additions of Bi₂O₃ were included up to 15 wt. %. Afterward, the glass structure, thermal properties, bioactivity, chemical compositions, and radiopacity were investigated through XRD, Rietveld analysis, DSC-TG, immersion on simulated body fluid (SBF), XRF, and radiopacity analysis by the ISO13116:2014 norm. The obtained results showed that glass thermal properties and crystalline structure change considerably after additions over 9.09 wt. % of Bi₂O₃. Furthermore, radiopacity was increased by ~3.6 times and represents the lower changes in thermal and structural glass characteristics. Despite the reduced bioactivity, the radiopaque BG followed a similar behavior of commonly used biomaterials such as hydroxyapatite.

Keywords: Bioactive glass 45S5[®], Bi₂O₃, radiopacity, bioactivity.

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Fabrication of Gelatin/Tannic Acid/Bioactive glass nanoparticles Hydrogels

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogel is a water-swollen, and cross-linked polymeric network [1]. The extensive interest in synthetic hydrogel technology in recent years has led to the rapid development of hydrogel technology, resulting in many hydrogels with different physical, chemical and biological properties [2]. As a result, hydrogels with different properties are widely used in biomedical fields, including drug delivery systems, tissue engineering scaffolds, wound dressings, biosensors, and systems for the separation of biomolecules or cells [1, 2].

As a derivative of collagen, gelatin exhibits biodegradability and good biocompatibility, and is able to form a hydrogel directly after dissolving in hot water and cooling [3]. However, the neat gelatin hydrogel shows weak mechanical properties and can be dissolved under body temperature [3]. Therefore, gelatin-hydrogels are commonly subjected to cross-linking treatment [3].

On the other hand, bioactive glass is a well-established biomaterial for bone regeneration with osteoinductive ability to form hydroxyapatite to bind tightly to bone tissue in the service environment [4-7]. Bioactive glass can also be doped with therapeutic ions and delivered drugs (porous bioactive glass particles) for therapeutic purposes other than bone repair [8, 9]. Furthermore, different therapeutic purposes and clinical service environments require different forms of bioactive glass, such as bioactive glass scaffolds, composite scaffolds, composite fiber mats, composite hydrogels, injectable materials, etc.

In this study, primary amine groups are grafted onto the surface of mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles. The amidated mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (AMBG) were dispersed in an aqueous solution of gelatin (G) which also contains primary amine groups. Tannic acid (T) was added as a cross-linking agent to the above suspension to fabricate G/T/AMBG hydrogels, due to the o-phenolic hydroxyl structure contained in the tannic acid which undergoes Michael addition reaction and Schiff's base reaction with the primary amine group [10] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Michael addition reaction and the Schiff's base reaction between o-phenol group and primary amine group.

Keywords: APTES, Gelatin, Hydrogel, Mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles, Tannic acid,

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Cerium Containing Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Nanoparticles for Biomedical Applications: Biocompatibility, Anti-Inflammatory, and Anti-Bacterial Activity

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ABSTRACT

Mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) are receiving great research interest for bone regeneration applications¹. The biological capabilities of MBGNPs can be enhanced by the addition of therapeutic ions. In this regard, cerium (Ce) is a promising candidate therapeutic ion for biomedical application due to the multifunctional biological properties of Ce ions, including anti-bacterial and anti-inflammatory activity². In this study, Ce-containing MBGNPs were synthesized using two different approaches. In the first approach, cerium was added to the glass system in-situ during the synthesis, while in the second approach cerium was added to the as-synthesized MBGNPs by using a post-modification method. SEM and TEM images confirmed that the different methods of synthesis influenced the morphology and textural properties of MBGNPs. All samples exhibited spheroidal morphology and disordered mesoporous structure. The average diameter of the MBGNPs was in the range of 100–200 nm. The influence of different methods of synthesis on ion release behavior and protein adsorption capabilities of MBGNPs were also studied. The obtained Ce-containing MBGNPs were non-cytotoxic towards pre-osteoblast MC3T3-E1 cells in contact with nanoparticles in the concentration of up to 100 µg/ml. Anti-inflammatory effect of Ce-containing MBGNPs was studied using lipopolysaccharides (LPS)-induced pro-inflammatory RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. The release of nitric oxide in the culture medium, which indicates the anti-inflammatory response of macrophage cells, was decreased significantly with the addition of Ce-containing MBGNPs. Anti-bacterial activity studies using *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) and *E. coli* (Gram-negative) bacteria showed that the Ce-containing MBGNPs reduced the bacteria viability for both bacteria strains. The mentioned features of the obtained MBGNPs make them useful in a variety of multifaceted biomedical applications, considering their biocompatibility, anti-inflammatory response, and enhanced antibacterial effect.

Keywords: Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Inflammatory, Bioactive glass, Cerium, Mesoporous, Nanoparticles

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Self-healing Hydrogel Based on κ -Carrageenan for Biomedical Application

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogels have become an incredibly prolific area of research in the field of medical technology and regenerative medicine. However, conventional hydrogels implanted within the load-bearing and dynamic environments of the human body are thus inclined to acquire some minor defects, which gradually propagate and grow in size and will ultimately lead to failure of the material if they are not repaired in due time. Conventional hydrogels are considered to be mechanically weak (toughness $<10 \text{ J m}^{-2}$), which limits their applications in medicine since tissues natural hydrogels possessing high toughness ($1,000 \text{ J m}^{-2}$) and high tensile strength (30 MPa). So, it will be necessary to make tough hydrogels with the ability to rapidly remedy material defects to achieve optimal implant lifetime. Self-healing techniques can be alternative routes to repair naturally damages and return to a normal state without the need for external stimulus. Furthermore, κ -Carrageenan self-healing hydrogel relies on the dissipation of energy by dynamic bonding, either intramolecular interactions or intermolecular interactions or dynamic covalent bonds.

This work presents κ -carrageenan double network (DN) hydrogel with self-healing features and focuses on natural chemicals like carrageenan to form a hydrogel which will be evaluated by physicochemical assessment and in vitro assay.

Keywords: κ -Carrageenan, Self-healing, Double network, Hydrogel

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Chitosan-Zn Complexes for Wound Healing Applications

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ABSTRACT

The repair of a wound is a dynamic process involving various cell types. Chitosan is an antibacterial, biocompatible and hemostatic natural material, which gained interest in wound healing applications. The ability of chitosan to form complexes with the help of amino and hydroxyl functional groups further enhances its features by addition of therapeutic ions.

In this study, chitosan was chelated with different amounts of zinc (6 and 12 % saturation of amino groups) by the in-situ precipitation method. The distribution of zinc in the chitosan matrix and its effect on structural properties were characterized by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, respectively. The dissolution behaviour of the complexes was investigated in lysozyme-containing Tris and acetate buffer. The biocompatibility of fabricated complexes was assessed with stromal cells: no apparent toxicity has been observed. According to the scratch test, the complex containing a lower amount of zinc showed the highest closure of the wound area compared to the control group. The fabricated complexes also exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) bacteria. The vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) release from stromal cells facilitated the assessment of the angiogenic potential of the complexes. The release of zinc enhanced VEGF secretion compared to the positive control group. To evaluate the anti-inflammatory potential of the complexes, nitric oxide (NO) secretion from macrophages was measured. The NO secretion was concentration-dependent: zinc addition caused a slight decrease of NO secretion. The presented results indicate that the developed Chitosan-Zn complexes could be suitable candidates for wound healing applications.

Keywords: Chitosan, Complexation, Zinc, Wound healing

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Zinc-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles for tissue regeneration

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ABSTRACT

Bioactive glasses represent a group of famous, widely studied and used biomaterials for tissue regeneration. Low-temperature derived sol-gel nanoparticles have attracted interest as promising novel therapeutic and regenerative agents. In addition to the advantages of bioactive glass nanoparticles (BGNs) themselves, they offer the possibility to incorporate various therapeutic inorganic ions which increase the specific biological properties (e.g., angiogenesis, osteogenesis). Zinc plays a crucial role in the formation, mineralization, development and maintenance of healthy bones. Moreover, it is involved in homeostasis, angiogenesis and antibacterial action and it is strongly connected with wound healing processes.

In this study zinc-doped system with the composition $62\text{SiO}_2 - 30\text{CaO} - 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 - 5\text{ZnO}$ (mol%) was synthesized and characterized for their structural, morphological, elemental and antibacterial properties. Compared to the previous results¹, the presented composition shows a relatively high content of Ca^{2+} ions (up to 30 mol%) that has been successfully incorporated by controlling the sol-gel synthesis conditions (nature of the solvent, stirring time, order of reagents, etc.)². Nanoparticles below 80 ± 20 nm have been fabricated and the addition of zinc did not influence the amorphous structure of the glass. The BGNs after immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF) mineralized to the apatite phase. The presence of zinc did not inhibit the hydroxyapatite formation, confirming that the zinc-doped BGNs retained their bioactive properties. The formation of HAp was further confirmed by the SEM, XRD and Raman spectroscopy. Antibacterial properties against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria have been evaluated and the antibacterial effect, as well as the inhibition of biofilm formation by *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, have been confirmed. The prepared glasses can be thus considered for the fabrication of polymer matrix composites and as the functional coatings for implants for biomedical applications.

Keywords: bioactive glass nanoparticles, sol-gel, zinc doping.

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PCL micro and nanofiber composites: effect of fiber diameter on *in vitro* bioactivity

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ABSTRACT

Electrospinning is a widely used technique in the field of tissue engineering to fabricate micro and nanoscale fibrous structures and their composites. Due to their 3D porous architecture electrospun scaffolds are considered as a structural imitation of extracellular matrix (ECM). Therefore, electrospun scaffolds fabricated from biocompatible polymers have potential role for guiding tissue regeneration¹. Also the addition of bioactive materials (hydroxyapatite- HA, bioactive glasses etc.) that can be embedded in the soft polymer matrix makes the composite scaffolds an effective platform for tissue regeneration both *in vitro* and *in vivo*². Previous studies revealed that cells are sensitive to surrounding mechanical environment. Especially, fiber diameter and morphology of the electrospun scaffolds influence cell adhesion, proliferation and orientation³.

Therapeutic ion-doped mesoporous bioactive glasses have been studied as novel candidates for incorporation in the polymeric matrix because of their excellent bioactivity, drug loading capacity, and release of therapeutic ions. Recent studies also showed that copper ions (Cu²⁺) have a significant role in the preparation of biomaterials due to their antibacterial, antimicrobial, angiogenic, and wound healing properties⁴. In this study, we prepared Cu-doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (Cu-MBGNs) by an emulsion-based sol-gel method. The Cu-MBGNs were used to fabricate poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL)-based electrospun fibrous composites, using optimized parameters of the electrospinning. The amount of Cu-MBGNs (15 wt% with respect to the amount of the polymer) incorporated into the polymer matrix were same for nano and micro fiber PCL composites. The diameter of electrospun fibers was tuned to adjust the mechanical environment within the fibrous structure. The average diameter of the fabricated fibers was in the range of ~200 nm and ~1 μ m for nano and micro fiber composites respectively.

Afterwards, ion release and cell interactions with the composite fibers with different fiber morphology were studied. The acellular bioactivity (SBF study) of the Cu-MBGNs and composite fibers was also investigated. The SEM images confirmed formation of hydroxyapatite (HA) like crystals *in vitro* on the surface of Cu-MBGNs. In composite nanofibers with incorporated Cu-MBGNs the *in vitro* mineralisation (HA crystal formation) was significantly reduced. No mineralization was observed for micro fiber composites. Inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES) analysis confirmed that the ions release from fibrous composites decreased with the increase of fiber diameters. *In vitro* biological study with murine bone marrow-derived stromal cells (ST-2) was performed to investigate the cell adhesion and proliferation on the composite mats. Cell viability on the fiber mats was assessed by using the WST-8 assay, using the neat PCL fiber mats (nano and micro) as the reference. Cell viability increased significantly with increasing fiber diameter. Fluorescence microscopy and SEM studies of fiber mats with attached cells confirmed the adhesion and proliferation of the cells on the fiber mat composites. Fluorescence microscopy imaging confirmed better cell penetration into the 3D network structure of scaffolds in microfiber composites compared to nanofiber structures. SEM imaging confirmed different nature of cell adhesion on micro and nano fiber composites.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, Copper, Electrospinning, Microfiber, Nanofiber, PCL Scaffolds

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Bioactive and biodegradable rod-like SBA-15 particles as support matrices for multifunctional composite systems manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

SBA-15 mesoporous silica has proven to be a very versatile material due to their unique properties. Its silanol-rich surface allows it to be organically modified with a variety of functional groups, acting as a protective matrix for sensitive molecules, making it suitable for a wide range of biomedical applications¹. This work explores the idea of developing SBA-15 rods with improved properties to be used as starting point platforms for multifunctional composite systems manufacturing. Particularly, this work is focused on studying the effect caused by adding glycerol as a co-solvent² and phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄)³. Solvent extraction was chosen for surfactant removal with the purpose of maintaining/producing a large amount of free silanols (SiOH) at the surface. Consequently, not only the presence of SiOH groups but also the H₃PO₄ content played a key role in bioactivity, when SBA-15 particles were immersed in simulated body fluid (SBF) at different time periods. Moreover, the rod particle size was modulated by the addition of H₃PO₄, being smaller as H₃PO₄ increased. Overall, SBA-15 rods are suitable and a good candidate to be used in the fabrication of complex structures that combine multiple functionalities among which can be included composite membranes, hybrid scaffolds and magnetically functionalized composites.

Keywords: SBA-15 mesoporous silica, silanol groups, H₃PO₄, multifunctional composite systems, bioactivity.

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Thermal analysis of aluminate glasses

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ABSTRACT

For successful preparation of glass ceramic and ceramic materials by controlled crystallization of amorphous powders or pieces of glass it is necessary to know detailed information about the crystallization kinetics of starting materials. Also for some, especially high-temperature applications, it is necessary to know the behavior of these materials at high temperatures. The knowledge of the effect of high temperature on microstructure, mechanical, physical and thermo physical and thermodynamic properties is vital for the successful preparation of such materials. Kinetic parameters such as apparent activation energy (E_a), nucleation rate (v_n), crystallization rate (v_c), induction periods for nucleation (I_n) and crystallization (I_c) as well as information about thermal behavior can be obtained by using suitable thermal method when examining a given material. Differential thermal analysis (DTA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetry (TG) are frequently used methods to investigate temperature changes in different materials [1 - 4].

Aluminate glasses have recently received increased attention mainly due to their excellent mechanical and optical properties. By crystallization of these glasses it would be possible to prepare ceramic materials with high thermal stability and chemical resistance. One of disadvantages of these materials is the problem of preparation larger pieces, because of their high melting temperatures and high tendency to crystallization [4].

In the present work we investigated the differences in thermal behavior of aluminate glasses with different alumina content in the Y_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 system. The yttrium aluminate glasses in the form of glass microspheres were prepared by combination of sol-gel method and flame synthesis. X-ray, SEM and PSA analysis were used for basic characterization of prepared systems. DSC and TG (isothermal and non-isothermal experiments) were conducted for detailed study of thermal behavior in temperature range 25 – 1300 °C. The crystallization of YAG ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$) phase was observed as the predominant process, and also crystallization of θ - Al_2O_3 phase was detected as another process in studied systems.

Keywords: DSC, TG, YAG, yttrium-aluminate glasses

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Study of thermal properties of inorganic materials

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ABSTRACT

For successful applications of new materials in practice, it is necessary to know their thermal behavior. This need often arises from applications of final materials (refractory ceramic materials, solid state lasers, turbine and automobile components), or so-called precursors are investigated for the preparation of larger ceramic or glass-ceramic pieces, in which sintering it is necessary to know their thermal properties or purity. Methods such as DTA, DSC, TG or their combinations (DTA-TG, DSC-TG) have been successfully used to study the thermal properties of materials. In this work, we will try to show the procedure of the equipment calibration and correct procedure of correction measurements. The main part of presentation will be devoted to sample preparation and correct measurement of thermal properties of selected samples, as well as the method of evaluating the measured data.

For thermal analysis, Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter equipment was used with two different DTA-TG and DSC-TG modes. The individual measurements were conducted in temperature range 35 - 1300 °C, with using of nitrogen or air atmospheres and with heating rates from 2 to 30 °C.min⁻¹.

Keywords: ceramic and glass ceramic materials, thermal analysis, DSC, DTA, TG

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HT XRD in Investigation of Thermal Behavior of Lanthanum - Aluminate Glasses

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ABSTRACT

High-temperature X-ray powder diffraction (HT XRD) is a frequently used method for investigation of phase transitions and structural changes during high-temperature processes. It allows examination of processes during the preparation and sintering of materials, the thermal stability or corrosion of materials. This method can be also used to investigate changes in lattice parameters and the size of crystals with increasing temperature and time, so that the suitability of various materials for high temperature applications can be assessed [1]. The combination of the results of HT XRD with thermal methods and SEM analysis allows the selection of conditions of heat treatment of glasses for the preparation of glass-ceramic materials [2, 3].

In the present work, two systems of lanthanum-aluminate glasses with different contents of Al₂O₃, specifically with 50 mol % (sample ALa1) and 76.2 mol% (sample ALa2) of Al₂O₃, in the form of microspheres were prepared by a combination of sol-gel Pechini method and flame synthesis [4]. The influence of this preparation method on the thermal behavior of the glasses was investigated by DSC, HT XRD and SEM analysis. X-ray analysis confirmed the presence of perovskite LaAlO₃ phase in both samples. In the sample with higher Al₂O₃ content, it also confirmed the presence of trace amounts of θ -Al₂O₃ phase. Thermal analysis showed one exothermic effect at 868 °C in the sample ALa1 and two exothermic effects at 920 and 936 °C in the sample ALa2. Based on the results of HT XRD we can attribute these exothermic effects to a specific phenomenon, namely crystallization of the perovskite LaAlO₃ phase, with crystallization occurring faster and in one step in ALa1, while in ALa2 the crystallization takes place in two steps. The presence and crystallization of the θ -Al₂O₃ phase may be also the cause of the slower crystallization of the perovskite phase in ALa2.

Keywords: lanthanum-aluminate glasses, HT XRD, XRD, DSC, SEM

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Sol-gel synthesis of Sm-doped zinc silicate glass-ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Zinc silicate glass-ceramics (GCs) have been ideal host matrices for optoelectronic materials with their long chemical stability, transparency and high band gap energy value (~ 5.5 eV) [1]. ZnO has unique mechanical properties by working as a network modifier in octahedral coordination and also as network former in tetrahedral coordination depending on the glass composition [2]. Another functional additive material is Sm³⁺, a rare-earth metal ion, for optical applications of GCs due to its special electron configuration in 4f shell. In this study, we report the fabrication of Sm³⁺ doped zinc silicate GCs by the sol-gel process, the effect of the composition ratio and the sintering conditions on the crystallinity and the optical properties of these materials.

The pristine and Sm³⁺ doped zinc silicate GCs were synthesized with a particular sol-gel route based on the hydrolysis of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), zinc acetate (Zn(Ac)) and Sm³⁺ acetate (Sm(Ac)). The compositional ratios of the glass ceramics were set by two starting solutions (Sol A and Sol B). The molar compositions of the samples are given in Table 1. After hydrolysis, the final solutions were placed in a furnace in Petry dishes at 45 °C for 4 weeks to obtain the xerogel. The samples were sintered in a muffle furnace at temperatures between 450-950 °C for 2 h.

Table 1. List of samples and their compositional ratio.

No	Composition	Mol. %
GC1	ZnO: SiO ₂	5:95
GC2	ZnO: SiO ₂	10:90
GC3	Sm: ZnO: SiO ₂	0.5: 5: 95
GC4	Sm: ZnO: SiO ₂	1.0: 5: 95
GC7	Sm: ZnO: SiO ₂	0.5: 20: 80
GC8	Sm: ZnO: SiO ₂	1.0: 20: 80

Fig 1. a) TG-DTA curves of the GC2 xerogel and b) Raman measurement profiles of the GC2 xerogel and the sintered sample at 450 °C.

Thermo gravimetric and differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) have been carried out on xerogels by Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter, Germany) from

room temperature to 900 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min under N₂ atmosphere. In Fig 1.a, thermal analysis curves of the GC2 sample displayed that the mass loss took place mainly in 2 two temperature regions from 50 to 150 °C and 250 to 450 °C. The losses were related to evaporation of solvents in the first region and the release of the residual organic groups in the second region. The structural changes were displayed by comparing the Raman spectra of the xerogel and the sintered sample in Fig 1.b.

The crystalline properties were monitored with X-ray diffraction spectroscopy (XRD), conducted by an Empyrean diffractometer (PANalytical, Almelo, The Netherlands). The β -willemitite Zn₂SiO₄ (JPCDS, 14-0653) crystalline peaks became apparent above 850 °C in Fig. 2.a. [3]. The emission spectra of the Sm³⁺ doped zinc GCs under 402 nm excitation wavelength are presented in Fig. 2.b. There are three emission peaks at 565, 601, and 645 nm, corresponding to $^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{5/2}$ (magnetic dipole (MD) transition), $^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{7/2}$ (mixed magnetic-electric dipole transition) and $^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{9/2}$ (electric dipole (ED) transition), respectively. The transition at 645 nm ($^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{9/2}$) exhibited the highest intensity in the characteristic reddish-orange region, which suggests a higher asymmetry in the structure [4].

Fig. 2. a) XRD profiles of the xerogel and the sintered forms of GC2. b) Comparative emission spectra of GC1, GC3, GC4, GC7 and GC8.

The effects of the Sm³⁺ and the ZnO content on the physical and optical properties of silica-based GCs were investigated by Raman, XRD and PL measurements. In future work, more sintering experiments will be performed to enhance the optical properties due the effective incorporation of the Sm³⁺ ions to the ZnO NCs and the subsequent energy transfer.

Keywords: Glass-ceramics, Samarium, Doping, Sol-gel, Zinc Silicate.

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Sol-gel process for the synthesis of eutectic ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Due to their excellent properties such as fracture strength/toughness, high melting points, oxidation resistance, thermal stability as well as creep resistance at high temperatures, eutectic ceramics are widely used in high-temperature applications. A modified Pechini method was utilized to synthesize highly homogeneous $Y_2O_3-Al_2O_3-ZrO_2$ powders with different concentrations of ZrO_2 (up to 10 mol.%), serving as precursors for the preparation of materials with eutectic microstructures. For this purpose, $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ dissolved in deionized water was mixed with a $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution. An aqueous solution of citric acid and ethylene glycol was subsequently added. Some previous works revealed that synthesis temperature plays a detrimental role in synthesis of nano powders; however, there is no systematic study on the influences of temperature on the stability of sols and precipitation of nano powder. In this work, the effects of temperature on the synthesis of $Y_2O_3-Al_2O_3-ZrO_2$ powders were investigated. The results revealed that there is a critical temperature window between 75 and 85 °C where the sol is stable.

Keywords: Eutectic ceramics; synthesis; YAG.

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Rapid Sintering: BT Based Lead-Free Piezoceramics and Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Conventional sintering is the most common technique in piezoceramic industry for the sintering of different materials. However, to attain enhanced electro-mechanical properties, the sintering conditions i.e., the heating and cooling rates of 2-5 °C/min and dwell time of 2-4 h are generally required. In consequence, the time and/or energy consumption is significantly high and apparently the cost of the final product. Therefore, rapid pressure-less sintering (RPLS) and spark plasma sintering (SPS), that are capable of raising fast heating and cooling rates of 100 - 200 °C/min are investigated. The RPLS samples reached a relative density up to 94% with fairly good piezoelectric constant, $d_{33} > 400$ pC/N for BaTiO₃-based materials. The SPS samples reached full density but their piezoelectric properties worsened due to smaller grains (10-15 μm) as well as formation of cracks at dwell times > 30 min. The RPLS method is experimentally easier and cheaper, while the SPS can benefit from full density of the samples suitable for transparent piezoelectrics. Both techniques revealed their huge potential for large scale sintering in the piezoceramic industry, which can considerably shorten (~ 95%) the entire sintering time and energy consumption.

Keywords: Lead free piezoceramics, rapid pressure-less sintering, Spark plasma sintering, microstructure, piezoelectric properties

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Effect of Inversion Defects on Sintering of Magnesium Aluminate Spinel

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ABSTRACT

The structural defects have a significant impact on the sintering of ceramics; however, so far, point defects has attracted the most attention. In the present work, the influences of structural inversion and point defects on the sintering of MgAl_2O_4 have been studied. A commercial powder was subjected to high-energy ball-milling to induce MgAl_2O_4 crystal structure inversion; also, the structural defects were introduced by doping the powder with limited amounts of lithium hydroxide. Raman spectroscopy and X-Ray Diffraction results allied with Rietveld refinement to study the inversion of MgAl_2O_4 . The effects of structural defects on the sintering behaviour of the powder were measured in terms of the activation energy of sintering estimated by following the master sintering curve approach. The results revealed that the inversion of the spinel structure decreases the activation energy of sintering significantly. The incorporation Li^+ into MgAl_2O_4 may have a similar impact on the spinel structure and, in turn, the densification of MgAl_2O_4 . Moreover, transparent samples were produced using spark plasma sintering (SPS). The doped samples exhibited limited blackening, which indicates that introducing structural defects may also be beneficial for preventing carbon contamination during (SPS).

Keywords: Magnesium aluminate spine, sintering.

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Fluorescence of Dy³⁺-Doped Phosphate and Borophosphate Glasses with Various Modifiers

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ABSTRACT

Trivalent Dysprosium is a promising dopant in luminescent materials for white light applications due to its two prominent emission bands in the yellow (~570 nm) and blue (~480 nm) region of the visible spectrum. These emission bands originate from electric dipole $^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{13/2}$ (yellow) and magnetic dipole $^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{15/2}$ (blue) transitions, of which the first one is a hypersensitive transition, thus highly sensitive to the host environment, while the latter one is less affected⁽¹⁾.

Figure 1: Emission spectra of BP glasses (a), and P glasses (b) under 349 nm excitation wavelength.

Phosphate glasses are good host matrices due to their low melting temperatures and their high solubility for rare earth ions. However, they can be highly sensitive to humidity. The incorporation of alkaline earth ions, such as Ba²⁺ or Ca²⁺, in phosphate glasses improves their moisture resistance and the addition of B₂O₃ as second network former will enhance their durability as well⁽²⁾⁽³⁾.

In this study we present our investigations on the luminescent properties of Dy³⁺ doped phosphate and borophosphates with varying divalent network modifiers. Two sets of glasses are prepared by the melt-quenching technique. Series (A) has the molar composition 40MO–60P₂O₅ and series (B) 40MO–20B₂O₃–40 P₂O₅ with M=(Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ or Ba²⁺), both are doped with 0.1 mol.% Dy₂O₃. The structure and optical properties of these glasses are investigated by Raman and fluorescence spectroscopy and the fluorescence lifetimes are determined.

Figure 1 presents the emission spectra of both glass series under 349 nm excitation. The phosphate glasses show slightly stronger luminescence intensities than the borophosphate ones. The fluorescence lifetimes within one series correlate with the ionic field strength of the network modifier and the longest lifetimes are observed in Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ containing glasses.

The Yellow to Blue (Y/B) emission intensities ratio of the respective bands can be used as an indicator for the symmetry around the Dy³⁺ ions⁽⁴⁾ and it has been found that it varies with the ionic field strength of the cations: the higher the ionic field strength, the higher the Y/B ratio, the higher asymmetrical local coordination environment of Dy³⁺ ions in the glass host network⁽⁵⁾. The tailoring

of the Y/B ratio allows generating a light emission with appropriate color coordinates and color temperature that suits the applications in white light-emitting devices.

Keywords: borophosphate glasses, phosphate glasses, dysprosium, luminescence, Raman spectroscopy.

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Luminescence of sol-gel-based wide bandgap material doped with rare-earth elements

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ABSTRACT

Wide bandgap materials, like TiO₂, ZnO, SnO₂ and their possible nano-heterostructures combinations are frequently chosen for enhancing the water-splitting process and for modulating of n-n, p-p, p-n heterojunctions. These semiconductors have a wide bandgap, good chemical stability, and low photo corrosion. On top of that, each photocatalyst itself has a lot of variables that can significantly influence the effectivity of photocatalysis, like the size, specific surface area, pore-volume, pore structure, crystalline phase, structural dimensionality, and the exposed surface facets. For instance, ZnO and TiO₂ have similar properties: a bandgap around 3.2 eV. SnO₂ has a much higher band-gap, around 3.7 eV, but the position of its conduction and valence bands makes it a suitable material for a heterostructure with ZnO and TiO₂. It was shown that TiO₂/SnO₂ and ZnO/SnO₂ type-II heterostructures lead to efficient charge carriers' separation, resulting in a longer lifetime of both carriers, holes and electrons [1]. The most urgent task is finding a photocatalyst with an adequate bandgap to maximize the absorption of solar energy. Solar light consists of 5% UV light (300-400 nm), 43% visible light (400-700 nm), and 52% infrared light (700-2500 nm). To extend the wavelength range of the photoactivation towards visible light, a dopant ion is introduced into the structure. Such ions form a wide range of new energy levels below CB. The most common groups of dopants are transition metal ions and rare-earth metal ions. The role of many elements as dopants has been studied in the crystal lattice of wide bandgap semiconductors, especially in TiO₂. In the case of transition metals, additional energy levels are arising from their partially filled d-orbitals resulting in a redshift in absorption. Fe³⁺ induced the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ or ZnO prepared by sol-gel [21,22]. In the case of iron ions, more oxidation states come into account. Khan et al. showed that the redshift of the optical absorption in doped TiO₂ was the outcome of d-d transition of Fe³⁺ (²T_{2g} → ²A_{2g}, ²T_{1g}) and the charge transfer transition between interacting iron ions (Fe³⁺ + Fe³⁺ → Fe⁴⁺ + Fe²⁺). These Fe³⁺ 3d states in addition to oxygen vacancies and Ti³⁺ centres create band states, thereby favouring the electronic transition to these levels and resulting in narrowing of TiO₂ band-gap. A direct confirmation is the Urbach energy increase magnitude with the lowering in the band-gap of Fe³⁺-TiO₂. The production of hydroxyl radicals (OH[•] + h⁺ → OH[•]) which are the main scavengers for the photogenerated holes (h⁺) were monitored by photoluminescence techniques using terephthalic acid. The observed trend was implying that the doped powder produced an enhanced amount of OH[•] radicals under light irradiation, which helps in its highest photocatalytic activity against the degradation of methylene blue and 4-chlorophenol under UV and visible light irradiation [2].

Niobium is considered a promising dopant with its ionic radius of Nb⁵⁺ of 0.064 which is slightly larger than TiO⁴⁺ of 0.0605 nm. Therefore, Nb⁵⁺ works as an n-type dopant in TiO₂ lattice and generates additional carriers in its CB, which can notably increase photocatalytic performance. Copper was found to be an effective dopant for TiO₂. The doped TiO₂ samples show increased visible light absorption and higher photocatalytic activity compared to undoped TiO₂. Sajjad et al. successfully prepared mesoporous Cu-doped TiO₂ via a sol-gel method [3]. Further characterization indicated that Cu⁺/Cu²⁺ sites as interfacial Ti-O-Cu surface linkages reduced bandgap energy as well as efficient charge separation due to the formation of Ti-O-Cu bonding at the surface and the associated appearance of oxygen vacancies, resulting in higher degradation rate.

Compared to transition metals, rare-earth metals like Samarium with 4f, 5d, and 6s² states are considered as the ideal dopants to modify the crystal structure, electronic structure, and optical properties of TiO₂, which can effectively influence the positions, widths, and density of states of CB and VB. In the case of europium ions, an emission was clearly observed by the naked eye and associated with ⁵D₀-⁷F₂ of Eu³⁺ transition, other peaks corresponding to ⁵D₀-⁷F₁, ⁵D₀-⁷F₃, and ⁵D₀-⁷F₄ transitions are also present [4,5].

Keywords: doping, luminescence, rare-earth elements, sol-gel, wide bandgap material

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DFT Functionals for Modeling of Polyethylene Chains Cross-Linked by Metal Atoms. DLPNO–CCSD(T) Benchmark Calculations

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ABSTRACT

Density functional theory (DFT) functionals for calculations of binding energies (BEs) of the polyethylene (PE) chains cross-linked by selected metal atoms (M) are benchmarked against DLPNO–CCSD(T) and DLPNO–CCSD(T1) data. PEX-M-PEX complexes as compared with plain parallel PEX \cdots PEX chains with X = 3–9 carbon atoms are model species characterized by a cooperative effect of covalent C-M-C bonds and interchain dispersion interactions. The accuracy of DLPNO–CC methods was assessed by a comparison of BEs with the canonical CCSD(T) results for small PE₃-M-PE₃ complexes. Functionals for PEX \cdots PEX and closed-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes (M = Be, Mg, Zn) were benchmarked against DLPNO–CCSD(T) BEs; open-shell complexes (M = Li, Ag, Au) were benchmarked against the DLPNO–CCSD(T1) method with iterative triples. Three dispersion corrections were combined with 25 DFT functionals for calculations of BEs with respect to PEX-M and PEX fragments employing def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets. Accuracy to within 5% for the closed-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes was achieved with five functionals. Less accurate are functionals for the open-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes; only two functionals deviate by less than 15% from DLPNO–CCSD(T1). Particularly problematic were PEX-Li-PEX complexes. A reasonable overall performance across all complexes in terms of the mean absolute percentage error is found for the range-separated hybrid functionals ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP/D3(BJ)-ABC.¹

Keywords: Metals, Gold, Colloids, Noncovalent interactions, Basis sets.

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The Effect of Adding Ceramic Fibers on Wear and Mechanical Properties of Thermal Barrier Coatings

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ABSTRACT

The thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) are designed to provide the engines operating at higher temperatures. That is, they enhance the efficiency and improve the components life [1, 2]. Typical TBCs consist of Ytria (Y₂O₃) stabilized ZrO₂, named YSZ, as a ceramic top layer which acts as thermal insulation layer and a metallic bond layer of MCrAlY (M = Co, Ni, Fe or a combination of the elements) which plays the role of a resistant film against oxidation. In other words, the prevalent deposition of bond coat on the metallic substrate is performed to keep it from oxidation and enhance the adhesion strength of TBCs [3-4]. Air plasma spraying (APS) and electron beam-physical vapor deposition (EB-PVD) are two main methods implemented to deposit the TBCs. However, deposition process in APS is much more efficient and cost-effective, which has resulted in popularity of this method [4-5].

In various engineering applications, the surface of a component is exposed to mechanical degradations such as wear. A common definition for wear is the damage to, or material loss from, the surface of a solid as a result of relative motion between the surface and a counterbody. Most of the equipment which are used in industrial processing undergoes abrasive wear at high temperatures. Wear degradation could cause removal of material or plastic deformation, which impacts the maintenance costs of different engines. Even though the wear resistance is not considered as a material property, materials having high hardness and good impact toughness at the same time, are generally regarded as suitable materials for wear-resistant applications [6]. Wear-resistant coatings have been required increasingly by the industrial section over the recent years. Surface modification and deposition of different coatings are being implemented to enhance the tribological properties of materials in the engineering sector. Different processes of chemical/physical vapor deposition, laser/electron beam method, mechanical attrition and thermal spraying are being used in preparing wear-resistant coatings [7]. One of the methods which is used frequently in surface science and coating technology are thermal spraying due to their high good wear/erosion resistance, adhesive strength and unique microstructure. Thermal spraying is an economical solution for wear and corrosion problems of engineering products [8]. Among thermal spraying methods, the plasma spray is a widely used technique in producing ceramic coatings, which have been employed in wear-resistant coatings production on metallic substrates in the industrial sectors [9].

Compared to conventional materials, reinforced counterparts have better mechanical and thermal properties. Ceramic matrix and TBCs suffer from poor fracture toughness as well as weakness in the cohesive strength of the ceramic layer, which limits their range of application. A method to enhance the mechanical properties of ceramic coatings is the addition of reinforcing materials, for instance, ceramic whiskers or fibers, to the coating structure, which is able to improve wear behavior and mechanical properties of the coating by several contributing mechanisms namely fiber pullout and breakage [10-11].

This paper will focus on the mechanical and wear behavior of thermal barrier coatings, the methods of manufacturing wear resistant TBCs and the mechanisms of degradation resulted by wear in these materials. The effects of adding ceramic fibers to thermal barrier coatings and the tribological properties of resulted depositions will also be studied. The article will finally scrutinize the state of the art study of promoting the wear behavior of plasma sprayed YSZ coating by means of introducing Al₂O₃ whiskers.

Keywords: Thermal barrier coating, Ceramic fibers, Wear, Mechanical properties

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The influence of the autoclaving process on surface properties of inorganic-organic films

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ABSTRACT

Sol gel method involves conversion of solution-sol to gelation – gel and this method could be applied in different fields. This transformation from sol to gel can be controlled according to the desired application. This process allows preparation of various materials with different characteristics of coating surfaces. The main advantages of this method are homogeneity of prepared thin films, wide range of substrates with different sizes could be used and could easily control of the preparation parameters of sol [1].

The surface characteristics of thin films can be influenced by changing experimental factors such as the procedure for mixing the reactants and the temperature in the sol production.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the surface properties of inorganic-organic films prepared in six different methods from "TEOS-TriEOS-H₂O-HNO₃-IPA" system. In connection with the follow-up research aimed at testing the adherence of microorganisms to the surface of the prepared layers, it was necessary to determine the influence of the disinfection process on their surface properties.

The autoclaving technique was performed for 30 minutes to test their ability to withstand temperatures of 121°C and pressures of 110 MPa. Wettability, surface free energy, morphological features and surface roughness of prepared films were observed before and after this "test" and then compared. Water contact angle was measured by sessile drop method to evaluate the hydrophobic properties of the surface. Polar and dispersion component of the surface free energy were calculated by Owens-Wendt-Rabel Kaelble method. For this purpose contact angle was observed using measuring liquids as diiodomethane and the water. The morphological features and surface roughness of the thin films were obtained by AFM measurements.

Keywords: contact angle, roughness, sol-gel, surface free energy, surface properties, thin films

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